

BOOK REVIEW

by Jessica Dello Russo

The cover photograph for Italian anthropologist Augusto Ferraiuolo's *Religious Festive Practices in Boston's North End* is emblematic of the book's contents. It is an image of St. Anthony and the Christ Child, resplendent in gleaming robes of gold – real gold, in the form of dozens of rings, medallions, chains, and other precious objects – at the moment they are being showered with confetti. The saint does not simply gesture in benediction, but appears to wave a twenty-dollar bill that is taped to his left hand. Behind the saint and to the left, waves an American flag, as well as a glimpse of a multi-floor tenement building. What is particularly fascinating about the outdoor theatrical display (beyond the elevation of a venerated image, its embellishment with precious objects and parade through public space) is the complex message that it sends of compromise and adaptation to the environment in which the scene is set.

In the study that follows, Prof. Ferraiuolo examines a number of historical and sociological factors that contribute to his interpretation of this scene, which he correctly avoids labeling as simply "Italian American" and "Catholic," in order to focus on more complex and "multidimensional" aspects of contemporary "religious festival practices in Boston's North End." Ferraiuolo, above all, is interested in how these festivals are staged in their current manifestation, and takes great care to illustrate how, why, and where they occur at the dawn of the 21st century in a small neighborhood in Boston's historic core.

Prof. Ferraiuolo carried out fieldwork in the North End of Boston between 2002 and 2005 to study "how the Italian Americans ... negotiate identity by manipulating symbols." He quickly discovered that one of the self-proclaimed "Italian" neighborhood's most prominent and enduring "ethnic" features was the cycle of weekend street festivals held during the summer months (June-August). Each feast is sponsored by an Italian benevolent society that generally takes its name from the patron saint of the ancestral village of the society's members. The saint itself is represented at the feast by a painted plaster statue or picture that is carried in a procession through area streets, accompanied by marching bands and society members who offer images of the saint on small cards or pins in exchange for donations. Money donated in advance is often attached directly to the saint's robes on long streamers or "calendars." By the feast's end, the figure is often all but hidden below a flowing cloak of cash. Some of the larger societies are able to organize street fairs in conjunction with the event, as well as live concerts and other popular entertainment. The public is thus welcomed into a carnival-esque setting with fried dough, cherrystones, pizza, pasta, and cannoli, and an entertaining mix of Italian and Italian-American merchandise (a good opportunity, on the one hand, to purchase Italian music CDs; on the other, a chance to don not only Italian colors, but items proclaiming allegiance to the "Sopranos" and "Jersey

Shore"). In this mix of nostalgia and opportunity, Ferraiuolo seeks the various means by which members of these societies – most no longer resident in the North End today – collectively piece together an identity by "manipulating symbols" – a process that Ferraiuolo calls "ephemeral" because of the manner in which the identities are often "strategically" created, as well as the real or imagined limits of their setting in a tiny urban neighborhood that has experienced major changes over the course of its nearly 400-year history to its boundaries and social makeup.

The very marketable Italian character of the North End, as Prof. Ferraiuolo reminds us in Chapter 1, is a relatively recent phenomenon. His topographical survey of what he defines as a "confined space" of just over half a mile in length and width emphasizes how this particular area of Boston – one of the city's oldest and smallest – has long been characterized as an "ephemeral place." Indeed, for centuries, the neighborhood's strategic location in relation to Boston's waterfront and commercial center has been both a blessing and a curse for its residents. Even through the Colonial period the North End, populated by merchants, artisans and others involved in trade, was nearly an island, cut off from the peninsula of Boston by a canal dug from the original Mill Creek to the Town Cove. This canal was later filled during the early 19th century when a major landfill of the area of the old Town Dock and Faneuil Hall created a new industrial zone for warehouses, factories and transit lines.

The paradox of this new prosperity for Boston, Ferraiuolo finds, is that the "absorption" of the North End into the city center led to the "progressive decay" of the former from a prosperous urban district into a 19th century slum. An equally drastic "alienation" of the North End occurred a century later when hundreds of its buildings were demolished to cut a wide swath of empty land for an elevated highway. Soon thereafter, an entire inner-city neighborhood, the West End, often described as the North End's "twin," was demolished in a federally sponsored plan for Boston's "urban renewal" (several saints societies active in the West End were moved to the North End at this time). At this point, however, the North End's physical isolation became a rallying point for politicians and local residents, who could now trace the neighborhood's limits in seawater and steel. The redevelopment of the North End's former waterfront industrial zone and overall "gentrification" of the district beginning in the 1960s was tempered, in its earliest phase, by subsidized housing for the elderly and programs to encourage longtime residents to purchase buildings and remain in the North End. But by negotiating these terms, Ferraiuolo notes, "the urban renewal of the Waterfront in the North End became possible with the fundamental consent of its inhabitants" (p. 21). Though still in progress at the time of Ferraiuolo's fieldwork, the completion of the Central Artery/Third Harbor Tunnel Project (the "Big Dig") promises to inaugurate a new era of physical transformation, perhaps that predicted by Ferraiuolo as an "imagined community" (p. 21).